

EMERGING THREAT OF FOOD INSECURITY: IMPLICATIONS FOR THE NATIONAL SECURITY OF PAKISTAN

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Abstract

In recent years, food insecurity has become a critical concern for Pakistan's national security. With a growing population, diminishing agricultural productivity and increasing vulnerability to climate change the situation of food security in Pakistan is becoming worsening. Currently, one-third of pregnant women suffer from malnourishment and 25 per cent newborn fall prey to stunted growth. Shockingly, over 30 per cent deaths in newborn caused by malnourishment. This dire situation act as a ticking time bomb for the social unrest and internal instability—a threat acknowledged in the National Security Policy (NSP). This study aims to analyze the critical role of food security in Pakistan's national security, using qualitative methodology and both primary and secondary data. Moreover, the study employs Barry Buzan's Regional Security Complex Theory (RSCT) to establish that food insecurity is a regional issue and should be addressed through the combined efforts of the actors in South Asia. The findings of the study show that unequal access to the food triggers social unrest and push individuals toward violence. Additionally, it demonstrates that food insecurity hinders economic stability and consequently, weakens overall security. This study recommends that conventional concept of security must be expanded to include human security as a corner stone to the overall security architecture.

INTRODUCTION

Food insecurity has emerged as one of the most pressing challenges confronting Pakistan, with deep implications for its socioeconomic stability and national security. Addressing this challenge requires a multi-sectoral approach that goes beyond traditional agricultural interventions to include governance, climate adaptation, foreign investment, and trade. Current research highlights that food security impacts in Pakistan are influenced not just by farm productivity but also by the political will and quality of governance. For example, applying secondary data for 1973–2018 and primary survey data from 600 households, (Farrukh, 2021)

determined that more than 43% of Pakistan's population remains multidimensionally food insecure. That so large a segment of the population is unable to obtain enough, well-nourished, and affordable food highlights the imperative for sustainable solutions through efforts that are coordinated at the macro and micro levels.

Food insecurity can also fuel conflict and instability by perpetuating grievances that are associated with unequal access to food. In extreme situations, communities and people may be pushed to violence, which demeans the government's ability to ensure law and order. The classical concept of security, thus,

primarily concerned with territorial integrity and military capabilities, must then be extended to accommodate unorthodox threats that put people's welfare in jeopardy. This paradigmatic change has helped make the idea of "Human Security" more central, emphasizing the need to protect the health, survival, and overall well-being of individuals as a vital aspect of state security.

The food security concept itself is based on four basic pillars: availability, accessibility, utilization, and stability. Vulnerability in any one of these areas jeopardizes not only household welfare but national resilience as well. In the South Asian region, the challenge is especially severe since the region harbors over 1.17 billion people. India has a share of over 17% of this population, followed by Pakistan and Bangladesh with 2.5% and 2.4% respectively, while Sri Lanka and Nepal have growth rates of 1.3% and 1.1% respectively. While population growth has decelerated in the last few years, food demand is still huge, and it continues to put additional pressure on agricultural systems. As (Qaim, Bhutta, & Jehan, 2023) contend, food security and economic growth are interdependent processes, whereby shortcomings in one weaken the other. In South Asia, this has translated into a chronic dependence on staple foods, especially wheat, for national food security programs.

Therefore, food insecurity in Pakistan cannot simply be perceived as either an agricultural or a developmental issue; it is essentially a security issue. The failure to provide sufficient access to food not only threatens human existence but also poses the risk of sparking social instability, economic stasis, and political destabilization. It is therefore important to appreciate this interconnection between food and security when it comes to crafting sustainable policy aimed at securing both human well-being and state stability.

Understanding the Situation of Food Insecurity in Pakistan

Food Insecurity: A Rising Non-Traditional Security Threat

Insecurity by food means is growing as a severe non-traditional security issue in Pakistan now. It threatens the stability of the economy, public health and social cohesion. At present around 45% of the

population suffers from moderate to severe food insecurity. The rate of under-nutrition has increased from 17% (2004-2006) to 21% (2021-2023), a phenomenon unprecedented in South Asia. The crisis is underpinned by factors such as poor agricultural output, effects of climate change on it, economic and political instability, corruption and rapid population growth. These forces have led to widespread impact including diminished economic performance, increase in malnutrition and burden on health care and threat to social unrest (Shah, 2024).

Malnutrition and undernourishment are still entrenched. Child stunting, underweight, and wasting are still prevalent, particularly among Sindh and Balochistan's vulnerable populations. This worsening nutritional status is indicative of systemic issues in food distribution, health services, and education. The decline is especially troubling because no other large South Asian nation has seen a trend towards worsening at this magnitude in recent years (Shahid, 2024).

The causes of this crisis are climate change, inefficient agricultural planning, economic mismanagement, and political instability. For instance, the 2022 floods in Pakistan inundated more than a third of the nation, wiping out crops and leaving millions displaced. This disruption put a massive strain on already weak food supply chains and underscored the sector's susceptibility to climate shocks. In the meantime, fast population growth has overwhelmed agricultural productivity, while inflation rendered foodstuffs inaccessible to low-income families. (Qamer, et al., 2023).

The implications are far-reaching. Economic production is reduced as a result of low labor productivity and increasing health costs linked to malnutrition. Malnutrition is estimated to cost Pakistan around 3% of its GDP each year in terms of lost productivity and additional healthcare expenditure. Further, food insecurity feeds grievance and inequality, which in turn can lead to civil disturbance, especially among urban slums and strife-torn rural areas (Shahid, 2024).

Factors Causing Food Insecurity

Pakistan's food insecurity is rooted in the intersection of structural, environmental, and socio-

economic determinants. They involve old-fashioned agriculture, climate change, technology shortages, weak governance, and financial uncertainty. These factors are interrelated; for instance, outdated agriculture is worsened by climate shocks and restricted tech. Effective mitigation necessitates a comprehensive approach with reform and engagement-oriented policies.

Traditional Agricultural Practices: Lack of Innovation

The ongoing dependence on traditional and mostly obsolete agriculture practices in Pakistan, including unproductive irrigation systems and the planting of poor-quality seeds, highly contributes to less-than-optimal crop outputs in the entire agricultural sector. This is particularly difficult for smallholder farmers, who represent a significant majority of the agricultural workforce and are often deprived of access to new technologies, better inputs, and vital information. This restricted access further aggravates existing productivity problems, keeping these farmers from maximizing their production and limiting the country's overall agricultural productivity, thus affecting food availability and leading to food insecurity (Khan, *et al.*, 2022).

Additionally, old irrigation methods continue to be a major limitation on agricultural yields. Pakistan's agriculture is dependent on canal irrigation networks, most of which are poorly maintained and inefficient, resulting in waterlogging, salinization, and water non-uniformity. Conventional flood irrigation, which is the practice of most farmers, wastes water and constrains crop water use efficiency. Consequently, much of the cultivable land is impaired by soil erosion and decreased fertility, which decreases productivity and jeopardizes long-term sustainability. Uptake of new irrigation technologies like drip or sprinkler systems is limited because of high capital investment and limited awareness among farmers, particularly those holding small parcels of land (Pinto, Fernandes, & Maia, 2016).

Seed quality is one of the main determinants of yield, but numerous Pakistani farmers continue to use saved or poor-quality seeds, which are more susceptible to pests, disease, and weather stress. The low level of availability and use of certified high-

yielding varieties is one of the reasons for rising productivity, particularly in smallholders who have no access to improved inputs and extension services (Behera, 2015).

Astride these challenges is the suboptimal condition of Pakistan's agricultural extension system. Poor staffing, poor coverage, and underfunding have dramatically curtailed extension agents' capacity to offer prompt and pertinent advice to farmers. Consequently, most smallholder farmers lack knowledge of best practices in crop production, pest management, and climate-resilient agriculture (Talib, Ashraf, Chaudhary, & Ahmad, 2017).

Economic Factors: Cost and Benefit Imbalance

Economic instability casts a long shadow over Pakistan's agricultural sector and deepens the nation's food insecurity (Ashlyn, 2024). Economic instability casts a long shadow over the agricultural sector of Pakistan and makes the country even more food insecure. Widespread inflation and the ongoing depreciation of the domestic currency have tremendously pushed up the price of basic agricultural inputs, including fertilizers and machinery. This added cost burden discourages important investment in the agricultural sector, effectively limiting farmers' ability to adopt and apply modern methods of farming. As a result, the opportunities for increased food production are vast but remain significantly underdeveloped since the financial environment prevents uptake of the available technologies and practices that otherwise help augment yields and guarantee increased provision of food for the populace (Shabnam, *et al.*, 2023).

Apart from the increasing cost of inputs, an enduring imbalance between agricultural investment and reward dissuades people from taking part, especially small-scale farmers. Empirical observations indicate that in spite of growing production costs, farmgate prices tend to stay constant, reducing profit margins and driving most farmers into debt or out of agriculture. This has resulted in the abandonment of arable land and rural employment transition to low-paying non-farm sectors, lowering food production domestically and elevating food imports which are subject to global price swings (Han, Cui, Chen, & Fu, 2019).

Another important dimension is the restricted access to financial services and credit, particularly for farmers who work on a small scale. The farm sector in Pakistan is still dominated by informal arrangements, which do not make most farmers eligible for insurance protection or loans. Commercial banks find it too risky to lend to farmers because of poor documentation of land, market uncertainty, and absence of collateral. Consequently, investment in technology that raises yields, for example, higher seed varieties or drip irrigation, is very low. Formal credit is available to a limited number of smallholder farmers, and the majority rely on the informal sources, which provide high-interest rates and exploitative terms (Akram, Iqbal, & Hayat, 2020).

Depreciation of currency worsens the issue. As the Pakistani rupee depreciates, the price of importing critical agricultural produce and foodstuffs increases. Because the nation imports vast amounts of wheat, edible oil, and pulses to augment indigenous deficit, this leads to increased consumer prices, even with local production capacity idle. This develops a paradox when food is available physically in markets but economically out of reach to much of the population (Waleed, 2020).

Dilapidated Technology: Limiting Productivity

Pakistan's deepened scar of food insecurity is worsened by tech's near and distant absence. Advanced farming methods, precise and keen, could raise production, making bellies thin no longer wither with hunger, a vision bright (Hussain & Akram, 2020). Limited availability of modern mechanized farming machinery hugely undermines productivity, making farmers unable to maximize their yields and efficiency. In addition, the poor investment in agricultural research and development hampers innovation, which retards the adoption of better farming practices, crop varieties that are resilient to stresses, and efficient pest and disease control measures. This technological gap not only leads to lower aggregate agricultural production but also causes high post-harvest losses because of ineffective handling, storage, and transportation practices. Therefore, the failure to develop the agricultural sector leads to intensified difficulties in providing food for a growing population and

ensuring food security, entrapping the country in a vicious circle of low productivity and susceptibility. (Kazmi, 2024; Riyaz, 2024).

Pakistan's agricultural industry continues to rely heavily on traditional agricultural practices and has limited access to technology on a large scale, severely curtailing productivity improvements. Small-scale farmers, who represent the majority of the industry, usually are not in a position to invest in mechanized machinery or sophisticated inputs like high-yielding seed varieties and precision irrigation technology. The technology deficit confines their capacity to grow output and cope with climate stressors. The continued application of outdated physical labor and low-efficiency irrigation practices such as flood irrigation leads to low water use efficiency and reduced crop yields, which hinder food security progress (Schweizer, Giulio, & Burkhardt-Holm, 2019).

Pakistan's agricultural industry is under threat from a serious lack of investment in research and development (R&D). The absence of advanced farming methods, disease-resistant plant varieties, and effective pest control techniques stifles production and worsens food insecurity. Experts call attention to the fact that without major R&D investment, the nation will be unable to provide enough food for its burgeoning population. The Pakistan Fruit and Vegetable Exporters Association (PFVA) has requested the allocation of Rs3 billion for R&D in the horticulture industry to maximize crop yields and quality fruits. This investment is considered a must in order to create climate-resilient crops and farm modernization, thus providing sustainable food security (Hanif, 2023).

Governance and Policy Issues: Lack of Clear Agricultural Policy and Implementation. (RUDA)

Erratic agricultural policies, as well as their ineffective enforcement, are a major challenge to Pakistan's pursuit of food security. Although programs such as the National Food Security Policy and the Kissan Package were instituted to correct major flaws in the agricultural sector and increase food availability, their efficacy has yet been significantly diminished by existing bureaucratic inefficiencies and non-transparency in their implementation. These systemic vulnerabilities

frequently cause delays in fund disbursement, misallocation of resources, and ineffectiveness in reaching target beneficiaries. Therefore, the benevolent intentions of these programs are negated, and the urgently needed advancement in strengthening agricultural productivity, benefiting farmers, and guaranteeing stable food supplies is substantially hampered, continuing to fuel the problems of food insecurity nationwide (Noondani, 2025).

Unlawful agricultural policies and their poor implementation remains an immense hurdle in Pakistan's quest for food security. Policies like the National Food Security Policy (2018) and the Kissan Relief Package (2015) were developed to enhance agricultural yield, maintain steady food supplies, and alleviate the effects of poverty in rural areas. Still, such programs have predominantly underachieved because of administrative inefficiencies, poor monitoring structures, and poor coordination between federal and provincial authorities. Untransparency in allocation of resources has further resulted in the sidelining of smallholder farmers who constitute the backbone of the agriculture industry. These organizational issues slow progress and are a source of chronic food insecurity for rural and urban populations (Ahmad & Saboor, Food Security in Pakistan and Need for Public Policy Adjustments, 2022).

The Kissan Relief Package, launched with a budget of Rs. 341 billion, was to offer fertiliser and crop insurance subsidies to poor farmers. However, several assessments have found that the package did not reach the targeted beneficiaries to any great extent. The bigger landowners received disproportionate benefits from the subsidy, with the small farmers being caught up in bureaucratic hurdles and not being aware or having access to the application process. Political meddling, inadequate outreach by agricultural extension departments, and a top-down strategy further undermined the efficacy of this initiative. These weaknesses underscore the imperative for inclusive, farmer-centric policy designs with localized implementation strategies stressing equity and accountability (Rashid, 2024).

Population Growth: An Unmanageable Threat to Food Security

Pakistan's population is growing at an alarming 2% every year, the largest in South Asia, putting tremendous pressure on the country's food resources. Such fast growing population naturally fuels the demand for food at an increasingly faster rate. At the same time, the trend of growing urbanization results in the cultivation of fertile land for housing, industrial, and infrastructural development purposes, in effect reducing the land available for cultivation. This twin challenge - rising food demand in addition to declining agricultural land - produces a wide and growing gap between the country's ability to produce food and the continually increasing consumption demands of its people, further deepening the current food insecurity crisis. (Mudassar, 2022).

The rapid urbanization process in Pakistan resulted in the encroachment of fertile agricultural lands for residential, industrial, and infrastructural development. The process not only reduces cultivable land but also disturbs local food production systems. An urban expansion study based on Lahore indicated that land use patterns, influenced by urban expansion, have significantly changed, reducing agricultural activities and jeopardizing the food security of the area. The study underscores that urban agriculture has the potential to play a key function in alleviating food insecurity through the promotion of local food production and maintaining biodiversity (Anwar, Breuste, Ahmad, Aziz, & Aldosari, 2023).

In addition, urbanization of agricultural land has larger consequences for the country's food security. The Supreme Court of Pakistan was told that large-scale urbanization in Punjab has led to a considerable reduction in farm production, thus forcing higher food imports to ensure domestic supply. This change has converted Pakistan from a wheat-exporting nation to one that imported wheat worth USD 1 billion between July-March of FY2024 to prevent scarcity in the domestic market. Such trends highlight the urgent requirement for sustainable urban development and policies that protect agricultural land so that long-term food security is maintained (Sigamony, 2024).

These observations underscore the complex connection between food security and urbanization in Pakistan, where the need to develop must be weighed against agricultural conservation.

Culture of Wasting Food

Food wastage is a common and economically destructive problem facing Pakistan, with estimated 26% of the nation's total food production each year, worth a whopping \$4 billion, wasted. This enormous loss is further compounded by strongly rooted cultural traditions, such as the practice of having lavish feasts with excessive food preparation far in excess of necessary consumption requirements. In addition, a general deficiency in awareness and education about the effective practice of food conservation on both household and commercial levels makes a significant contribution to this issue. The blend of these cultural values and limited knowledge leads to a significant depletion of available food resources and economic capital, thus further eroding attempts at ensuring food security and sustainability within the country (Ahmed, 2024; Shah, 2024).

Food wastage is one of the common concerns in Pakistan, with cultural practices being one of the reasons causing major losses. Excessive food preparation and lavish feasts contribute to high pre-consumer and post-consumer wastage. Research in the hotel industry of District Swat found that around 694 tons of food are wasted every year, translating to a loss of over Rs. 243 million (Farooq, Ali, Khan, & Khan, 2023).

Insufficient Food Preservation Capacity

The insufficiency of storage space and the deplorable condition of transport infrastructure in Pakistan play a major role in causing significant post-harvest losses, ranging up to 30-40% of the overall agricultural output. The lack of cold storage facilities, especially for perishable items, results in wastage and spoilage before food can even be delivered to consumers. Additionally, the lack of effective and well-managed supply chains impedes the timely transportation of excess food from areas of abundance to areas of deficits. This supply chain bottleneck aggravates food

insecurity by inhibiting fair distribution and ensuring that much of the harvested food never reaches the most needy, further taxing the country's food resources (Kazmi, 2024; Noondani, 2025).

A recent study by the Asian Development Bank reports that Pakistan loses more than \$1 billion every year in post-harvest losses, especially in fruits and vegetables. The losses are due to poor handling of perishable products, inefficient transport, and poor storage facilities and market infrastructure. The report underscores the importance of having a national agriculture production information system to offer reliable information on production and prices to enable quality decision-making and minimizing such losses (Ahmed A. , 2019).

Additionally, the insufficient processing infrastructure aggravates the issue. Principal scientific officer at the National Agricultural Research Centre (NARC) Dr. Hidayatullah mentions that around 35% to 40% of Pakistan's output is lost after harvesting as a result of improper handling, inefficient transportation, and low-quality storage facilities. He recommends investment in processing infrastructure and capacity-building programs to enable farmers to retain higher value from their produce, increase shelf life, and improve marketability (Ahmad, Afridi, Khan, & Sarwar, 2021).

This is compounded by the unavailability of cold storage facilities, particularly in rural areas. It is estimated by the Sindh Enterprise Development Fund that about 25% to 30% of the total agricultural produce in Pakistan gets wasted because of post-harvest handling problems, and a major reason for this is the non-availability of proper transportation and cold storage facilities. The report highlights the urgent need for good quality cold storage facilities to maintain the quality of agri-produce and minimize wastage (Shafiq, Ahmad, & Hamza, 2024).

In addressing these issues, a multi-pronged approach involving investment in new storage technology, strengthening transport infrastructure, and training farmers in efficient post-harvest practices is needed. It is critical to undertake these measures to cut down wastage of food, enhance food security, and strengthen the agrarian economy of Pakistan.

Food Insecurity: Implications for National Security of Pakistan

Food insecurity in Pakistan has transcended economic and social determinants and turned into a critical national security concern. The repeated inability to supply adequate food access to all citizens weakens the stability of society, economic growth, and national resistance to internal and external hostilities. In this chapter, the convoluted ramifications of food insecurity for the national security of Pakistan are analyzed on the basis of latest research studies and policy studies (Ubaid-ur-Rehman, Asghar, & Khalid, 2021).

Recent studies highlight that food insecurity in Pakistan is not just an economic issue but a diverse threat to national stability. The convergence of food shortage with socio-political factors further multiplies vulnerabilities, necessitating policy responses targeting food security as part of the overall national security agenda.

In addition, the loss of agricultural resources, together with poor policy interventions, has worsened the food crisis. The failure to pursue sustainable agricultural practices and not changing with climatic conditions have made a mostly agrarian nation a food resource-deficient country (Mehdi, 2024).

The Nexus between Food Insecurity and National Security

Food insecurity directly impacts national security through several pathways:

Social Unrest and Political Instability

Food insecurity can cause political instability and civil unrest. Food price increases and shortages have, in the past, activated riots and protests in Pakistan. There is evidence that political instability has a negative effect on food access and production, resulting in food insecurity and poverty on a high scale (Munir, et al., 2024).

Studies have shown that sudden increases in food prices or shortages can act as catalysts for civil unrest. In Pakistan, such events have historically led to demonstrations and riots, highlighting the direct link between food security and political stability (Khalid, 2018).

In addition, the interaction between political instability and food insecurity forms a vicious cycle. Political unrest upsets food production and supply, which further worsens food shortages, hence increasing instability. Combating this cycle calls for overall strategies that include political reforms as well as food security approaches (Shahid, 2024).

Economic Vulnerability

Agriculture is a significant contributor to Pakistan's GDP. Food insecurity adversely affects agricultural productivity, leading to economic downturns and increased dependence on imports. The share of the agriculture sector to GDP is 20% (Azeem, Muger, & Schilizzi, 2016).

Even though Pakistan is an agrarian economy, it suffers from widespread food insecurity. This irony is the result of inefficient agricultural methods, insufficient investment in rural infrastructure, and policy failures, which all serve to destabilize the economy (Parveen, Tufail, & Salman, Impact of Demographic Vulnerabilities and Socio-Economic Resilience on Food Insecurity in Pakistan, 2022).

The financial implications of food insecurity go beyond agriculture. It impacts labor productivity, drives up healthcare expenditure in the form of diseases caused by malnutrition, and requires increased food imports, hence putting pressure on foreign exchange reserves.

Health and Human Capital

Food scarcity and malnutrition reduce the health level of the population, reducing productivity levels of the workforce and health needs (Azeem, Muger, & Schilizzi, 2016). Nutritional disorder reduces the ability to work and human capital, raising the susceptibility of nations to poverty (Siddiqui, Salam, Lass, & Das, 2020).

A large segment of Pakistan's population—most notably women and children—are affected by calorie and micronutrient deficiencies, which affect not just physical condition but cognitive development and subsequent educational performance. For instance, one study conducted in rural Pakistan reported that about 30% of women of reproductive age had low plasma zinc levels, and more than half were anemic—states that are highly associated with compromised immune function and delayed development in

children when maternal nutrition is suboptimal during pregnancy (Brazier, et al., 2020).

In addition, examination of dietary information among rural women and girls showed that over 50% of young women were anemic, 38% had iron-deficiency anemia, 32% were vitamin A deficient, and over 80% had deficiencies in other important micronutrients. These common shortfalls of nutrients lead to stunted growth as well as impaired cognitive functions among children, hence the reduction in overall human capital and economic productivity in the long run (Baxter, Wasan, Hussain, Soofi, & Ahmed, 2021).

Strategic Autonomy

Dependence on foreign food sources erodes national sovereignty and can be geopolitically manipulated. Food security challenges in Pakistan are typically compounded by political and economic management issues, reaching governance of agriculture and population nutrition needs (Newman, 2018).

Dependence on imported food renders Pakistan vulnerable to the dynamics of global markets and export nations' trade policies. Such dependence can be strategically manipulated at the expense of national autonomy. Strengthening domestic food production through policy reforms and sustainable farm practices is necessary to break import dependence and enhance strategic autonomy. This does not only ensure food security but also enhances economic resilience (Fahad, et al., 2024).

Factors Contributing to Food Insecurity and Their Security Implications

Climate Change and Environmental Degradation

Pakistan's climate change vulnerability—defined in terms of erratic rainfall, floods, and droughts—has negatively impacted agricultural productivity considerably. These natural threats endanger food security and, by extension, national stability (Fatima, 2024). Climate-related disasters, including the 2022 floods, have inundated extensive areas of agricultural land, resulting in heavy crop losses and food shortages. These disasters point towards the need for climate-resilient agriculture strategies (Leghari & Salman, 2022).

Climate change adaptation demands holistic policies involving investment in water management,

research into drought-resistant crop types, and farmer education on sustainable methods. This is essential to achieve long-term food security (Safdar, Shahid, Yang, & Rasul, 2024).

Population Growth and Urbanization

Pakistan's population growth and urbanization have led to an increase in the demand for food, and land utilized for crops being converted for non-agricultural purposes, exacerbating food scarcity and potential for resource-based conflict (Jabeen, 2024).

As Pakistan's urban areas grow, large areas of productive agricultural land are being turned into residential and commercial estates. A case study in Lahore determined that the rapid suburban expansion of 2001 to 2020 decreased agriculture land from 50% to 34% in important peri-urban areas, with a direct impact on local capacity for food production and placing additional pressure on distant rural producers to supply urban demand (Anwar, Breuste, Ahmad, Aziz, & Aldosari, 2023).

Also, the reduction in arable land has driven food provisioning systems toward dependence on food imports and concentrated supply chains, which are more susceptible to price shocks and logistical breaks. Research illustrates that in Lahore, food security among poor urban households has strong correlation with the disappearance of urban agriculture activities, highlighting that policy support for urban agriculture and local food distribution should be promoted (Farooq & Rashid, 2024).

Economic Disparities and Poverty

Large poverty rates limit access to healthy food, leading to malnutrition and discontent. Economic inequalities have the following effects: They can spur grievance, which in turn destabilizes places and destabilizes national unity (Ahmed, et al., 2024).

Inequality of income and high poverty lower the availability of healthy food in most Pakistani households. Another study on PSLM 2019–20 data revealed that households living under the poverty line were highly vulnerable to experiencing food insecurity and that income status, household size, levels of literacy, and headship characteristics were

major determinants of food security (Shair, Afzal, Ahmad, & Iftikhar, 2024).

Sustained economic inequalities also widen urban-rural gaps in food security. Evidence shows rural farm household land ownership is common, yet low market integration and thin incomes enhance exposure. Urban poor households, on the other hand, have restricted access to healthy food despite being physically available. Specialized social protection interventions specific to such situations have been effective in limiting food insecurity (Kibria, Khan, Aleem, & Haq, 2023).

Policy and Governance Challenges

Inadequate agricultural policies, inadequate rural investment in infrastructure, and inadequate mechanisms of food distribution have led to chronic shortages of food that stress the state's capacity to provide and sustain order for its people (Sriram & Naz, 2025).

Policy dealignment and poor implementation have been seen as significant hurdles to food security. A review of Pakistan's National Food Security Policy (2018) uncovered that while the policy framework is adequate, absence of enforcement, inter-agency coordination, and monitoring mechanisms have hindered advancement. Institutional capacity and governance building are a must for bridging this policy-practice divide (Parveen, et al., 2023).

Furthermore, empirical evidence emphasizes good governance as a key to providing equitable food access. A study showed a strong negative relationship between bad governance—like corruption, food stockpiling, and poor border control—and food security at the household level. Improving transparency, accountability, and anti-corruption practices in food supply chains directly enhances availability of food and mitigates social tensions (Khan, Bojnec, Daraz, & Zulpiqar, 2024).

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study has examined the emerging threat of food insecurity and its direct and indirect consequences to the national security of Pakistan. Based on multiple sources of academic literature and policy reports, the study verifies that food insecurity is no longer an economic or developmental issue only; it is a

multidimensional threat that compromises social stability, economic resilience, health outcomes, and strategic autonomy.

The examination illustrates that food insecurity is a cause of political unrest in that it triggers civil uprising, especially when food prices increase or supply declines. It also erodes economic stability through lowered agricultural output, greater reliance on imports, and heightened poverty. In addition, food insecurity reduces human capital by way of malnourishment, stunting, and negative health outcomes. Domestic dependence on food imports also exposes the nation to price variability across the world, lessening its strategic independence and geopolitical security.

Many internal factors have been recognized as the underlying causes of Pakistan's food insecurity: archaic farming methods, climate change, inequality in economic terms, infrastructure deficiencies, policy failures, urbanization on agricultural land, and cultural food wastage. In addition, poor governance and implementation breakdowns have hampered the effectiveness of current food-related policies.

Dealing with these challenges calls for an integrated, strategic, and multi-sectoral response. There must be a clear synergy between food security policies and national security frameworks to avert civil war, promote social harmony, and secure the long-term welfare of the nation.

Recommendations

Strategic Measures to Enhance Food and National Security:

Agricultural Innovation

Improving food security through agricultural innovation needs long-term investment in research and development, especially in climate-resilient seed technologies, sustainable irrigation, and mechanization of agriculture. Pakistan's agriculture sector needs to adopt new practices like precision agriculture, which is based on the use of data and analytics for optimizing input and maximizing output. Innovations of this kind are the key to fixing challenges brought by climate change and resource degradation (Ullah, Nawaz, Farooq, & Siddique, 2021).

Latest research indicates that cutting-edge technologies like remote sensing, unmanned aerial vehicles (drones), and geographic information systems (GIS) are greatly enhancing decision-making at the farm level by raising monitoring efficiency and improving resource utilization. For example, intelligent agriculture solutions have been associated with raised crop yields and lower environmental impacts in several developing nations, including Pakistan (Manners, Blanco-Gutiérrez, Varela-Ortega, & Tarquis, 2020).

Capacity development among farmers, particularly smallholders, is needed to ensure equitable access to agricultural innovations. Training interventions that introduce farmers to digital platforms, mechanization equipment, and sustainable agriculture enable bridging the gap between technological access and utilization. Public-private partnerships are necessary to re-design extension services so that small-scale farmers are not excluded in the transition to smart and climate-resilient agriculture. South Asian evidence shows that farmer field schools, ICT-based training, and participatory research models have had a substantial effect on adoption rates as well as productivity (Shayan, Mohabbati-Kalejahi, Alavi, & Zahed, 2022).

Collaborative innovation systems involving the universities, research institutions, agritech start-ups, and the government can be the driver of high-yield and pest-resistant seed varieties. The collaborative settings also improve the bottlenecks associated with post-harvest storage and handling, which is especially important for poor farmers (Abbas, et al., 2021).

Policy Reforms

In order to have equitable food security, Pakistan has to shift its agricultural policies to be more favorable to smallholder farmers. This entails changing land tenure systems, improving access to formal credit, and offering focused subsidies. The policies should work towards making food systems more inclusive so that state support benefits marginalized groups—particularly women and rural workers (Parveen, Tufail, & Salman, 2024).

Recent policy reviews provide evidence on the need for open governance institutions in the case of agricultural subsidies and crop insurance schemes. In the absence of accountability and institutional

checks, these systems usually end up bypassing their target groups. Institutional frameworks need to be made stronger, especially at provincial and local levels, to make sure that public investments in food security are effective as well as equitable. South Asian research, such as that conducted in Pakistan, indicates that poor governance, bureaucratic ineffectiveness, and political interference often weaken subsidy schemes and insurance programs (Zelege, Beyene, Deressa, Yousuf, & Kebede, 2021). Decentralization can also allow for increased responsiveness to agricultural demands at the local level. Provincial and district governments are better able to apply locally based approaches that take into consideration regional climates and crop patterns. This transition towards local governance approaches has proved to enhance the allocation of resources and agricultural extension outreach. Additionally, the inclusion of farmer organizations in policymaking can enhance trust and make reforms based on realities on the ground. Participatory governance is particularly relevant in post-crisis situations where trust rebuilding within state institutions is crucial to policy effectiveness (Hone, et al., 2020).

Climate Resilience

Vulnerability of Pakistan to climate change requires a transition towards climate-smart agriculture (CSA). It encompasses the promotion of drought-resistant crops, enhanced water use efficiency, and investment in climate-resilient rural infrastructure. In addition to enhancing food production, CSA lessens greenhouse gas emissions, which is complementary to both mitigation and adaptation strategies (Shafeeqe & Bibi, 2023).

Community-managed water management schemes and localized adaptation plans are yielding positive results in South Asia. These systems contribute to limiting the reliance on unpredictable monsoon patterns through rainwater harvesting, micro-irrigation, and water-saving cropping practices (Lyu, Xu, & Sun, 2021).

Early warning systems, when coupled with real-time weather information and farmer extension programs, can initiate timely warnings and lower climate-related losses. These systems need to be complemented by contingency planning and

insurance programs so that farmers are in a position to rapidly bounce back from severe weather conditions. Agricultural planning also needs to consider the future climate situation through the adoption of climate data modeling and resilient infrastructure investment. This acts as a guarantor of sustainability and food production continuity under stress (Codyre, et al., 2025).

Social Safety Nets

Strengthened social protection mechanisms are an essential buffer against food insecurity, particularly in crises like natural disasters, economic shocks, or pandemics. Scaling up and modernizing programs like the Benazir Income Support Program (BISP) and Ehsaas can enhance targeting and minimize administrative leakages (Javed, Ahmed, & Amal, 2021).

Evidence affirms that, if well designed, conditional cash transfers and food assistance programs can cut malnourishment sharply and enhance household food security. National database-linked digital payment systems improve transparency and reduce errors of exclusion (Hussain & Schech, 2021).

World best practice highlights the need to incorporate nutritional objectives into social protection programs. For instance, voucher schemes favoring healthy food have the potential to have two-fold effects—combating hunger and strengthening public health outcomes. Global collaboration with development partners like the World Food Programme (WFP) and the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) can enhance program design, reach, and monitoring even more. The partnerships allow nations like Pakistan to reach out to the neediest more efficiently and with less constraint of resources (Öhman & Sund, 2021).

Pakistan national security environment is increasingly defined by untraditional threats like food insecurity. As this thesis has contended, food security is not simply a development imperative but rather a foundation of national resiliency. Strategic policy coordination, investment in innovation, and inclusive governance are required to transform food insecurity from a destabilizing influence into an opportunity for sustainable growth.

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